

SCIENTIFIC STUDY AND MATHEMATICAL STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF PROCESSES OF RADICALIZATION OF MILITARY PERSONNEL.

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Abstract. The article appreciates the processes of radicalism among military personnel and students of the military system, mathematical analysis and scientific reasoning through a survey.

Noncommissioned officers (50) and cadets (50) were selected as respondents in order to scientifically investigate the processes of radicalization of military personnel.

The aim of the survey is to develop recommendations and scientifically based proposals to solve the problem of radicalization of military personnel, primarily the development of empirical theoretical formulas based on mathematical-statistical laws between the upper and lower ranks, with at least two parameters. Similar, based on the laws of correlation between groups, is to develop regression equations in order, as a result, to diagnose with great accuracy the phenomena of radicalism that may appear in the current and future military. In today's conditions of globalization and the existence of conflict situations and conflicts at the international or regional level, the issue of combating destructive ideologies such as extremism, radicalism and terrorism is one of the current issues on the agenda. This is because most of the people who come under the influence of extremist and radical ideas are young people and their number is increasing. "Radicalism" – (Latin "vein", "root", "core") means a sharp, uncompromising realization of a goal, the striving to radically change the existing situation in one or another work. Radicalism is a process that consists of the desire to fundamentally and uncompromisingly change the existing social, political and cultural situation of a particular person or group. Psychologists say that young people act on the basis of inexperience and emotions, i.e. H. changes in their mental state due to external influences; rapid depression and intolerance to emotional shocks; to be completely removed from the attention of loved ones; A number of factors, such as extreme curiosity and inability to fully analyze information, and gullibility can promote the process of

radicalization. Among the reasons why young people get involved in various currents, it is also necessary to highlight moral and spiritual factors, such as their knowledge, including their desire to acquire everything at once and everything (wealth, fame, career, etc.), in scientific terms Maximalism. It should be noted that different directions and measures are taken to counter threats in countries around the world. In particular, our government has organized corresponding activities in Uzbekistan. In this regard, it can be noted that this was determined by the adoption of high-level documents aimed at preventing the spread of radical and extremist ideas among the population, especially among young people.

In particular, the 82nd goal of the State Program for the Implementation of the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in the “Year of Attention to the People and Quality Education”, approved by the Decree of the Resident of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 28.02.2023 “Effective Mechanisms to combat extremism and terrorism” were named. Within the framework of this direction, the task is to organize activities to form strong and stable immunity in the fight against extremism in the young generation

was transferred to the relevant authorities. As a practical expression of this, under the motto "Enlightenment against Ignorance", to ensure the stability of the social and spiritual environment, strengthen interreligious and international harmony, fight against the ideas of terrorism and extremism, representatives of The Committee on Religious Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, professors-teachers of the International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan, Imam Vukhoryu of our country, Imam Termizi and Imam Moturidi, international scientific and research centers, are engaged in events for spiritual and educational promotion. Propaganda activities are organized by representatives of state and public organizations of the republic, town hall meetings, state and non-state higher and secondary educational institutions.

As part of these events, the practice of holding discussions among students from more than 100 universities on preventing the spread of ideas alien to Islam, subversive views and various ideologies that deny universal human values was introduced. At the same time, the processes of giving students explanations about the importance of virtue principles such as love for the country, respect for parents and teachers showed their positive state.

In addition, normative legal documents aimed at combating radicalism and extremism have been adopted in our country, and the implementation of these legal documents has contributed to the more effective functioning of existing

mechanisms in this direction. In particular, new requirements for measures to prevent extremism were introduced in our country on July 30, 2018 with the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Extremism". This law expanded the definitions of extremist activities, extremist groups and organizations, and the consequences of financing these activities.

On July 1, 2021, the National Strategy of Uzbekistan to combat extremism and terrorism for the period 2021-2026, adopted on the basis of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, was approved. The adoption of the national strategy can be interpreted as a historic event. The reason is that this document defined the specific directions for combating destructive evils in the conditions of the new Uzbekistan. Existing experience in combating extremism and terrorism in the strategy and in the region

The specific aspect of extremist and terrorist activities as well as national, social and religious situations were studied in Markaziu Osiuo and the situation in combating these threats in their countries was comparatively analyzed. The priorities of the national strategy were defined as follows:

- to promote the ideas of patriotism, traditional values and tolerance in order to prevent the spread of the ideology of extremism and terrorism;
- Preventing the spread of extremist ideas among minors and young people;
- Protecting women's rights and strengthening their role in the fight against extremism and terrorism;
- Protection of citizens staying abroad for a long time from the influence of extremism and terrorist ideas;
- Fight against the use of the global information network Internet for extremist and terrorist purposes;
- Ensuring the participation of civil society institutions and mass media in the fight against extremism and terrorism;
- Improve measures to prosecute and prosecute extremist and terrorist activities and their financing;
- Improving the normative legal framework in the field of combating extremism and terrorism;
- international and regional cooperation.

Each of the tasks and directions defined in the strategy shows that the goal is to comprehensively protect the population of our country, especially our future generation, from radical views. In addition, through the initiative of the leader of our country, within the framework of the framework program, thousands of convicts were amnestied, citizens were removed from various lists,

and more than 500 women and small children were brought to our country from conflict zones. The “More” speeches emphasize the value of man and his freedom is once again shown to be the highest value of society. It can be said that this served to increase the trust of some people in society towards their country and to create goodwill towards the state policies of the time, which was embodied in people's minds as goodness.

German nationalism, which was initially founded to support the cultural unity of Germans, became radicalized after some time and became extremist, racist, anti-Semitic, anti-democratic, full of hatred for the environment, "racial hygiene" - purifying the nation from "racial aliens" and "defective" elements morphed into the idea of totalitarianism – National Socialism, which includes tyranny and other negative vices. If we give an example of radicalization, a person's concern for his nation and his homeland, his desire for his development and freedom is a good feeling that can be an award for every person he is. However, if someone sets moral standards aside for the sake of such a pursuit, then he has left this circle - in the process of radicalization, he is exposed to extremism and other serious vices.

As President Shavkat Mirziyoev explained

“We will not allow any kind of radicalization in our society, no poisoning of the minds of our youth with destructive foreign ideas, no misuse of religion for political purposes, no replacement of enlightenment with ignorance” [1]

“So that our young people become independent thinkers, have high intellectual and spiritual potential and become people who are not inferior to their peers in any field of the world, we mobilize all the forces and capabilities of our state and society to be happy “we deliver” [2]

Results and analysis

We present the results of scientific research (observation) in the form of a table. There are basically one hundred survey questions and each question is worth 1 point or 1 percent. First of all x_1 - patriotism 24, x_2 - humanitarianism 14, x_3 - faith 17, x_4 - trust 18, x_5 - will 10, x_6 - pride 15, x_7 - compromise 8, x_8 - compassion consists of 4 questions, and each number out of a hundred is proportional to this percentage.

For example, 14 questions are given 14%. The appearance of this diagram is presented in the form of a histogram or graph, and we perform a mathematical statistical analysis.

We present the results of our scientific research (based on a survey) conducted in order to protect military personnel and cadets from the influence of radicalism under the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The results of questionnaires about the attitudes of sergeants and cadets to the processes of radicalism.

Table 1.1

Respondents	x_1	x_2	x_3	x_4	x_5	x_6	x_7	x_8	Total score%
Sergeants	20	12	5	14	9	13	7	2	82
Cadets	18	13	6	14	9	14	3	3	80
Volume of conducted surveys (frequency)	7	4	7	8	4	4	10	6	$n = 50$
Classical probability	0.14	0.08	0.14	0.16	0.08	0.08	0.20	0.12	$p = 1$

We compare the parameters of the cadets and the sergeants who are their leaders. X_i - variants of the obtained scientific research, n_i - frequency of the observed or studied object. Based on the results of table 1.1, we draw up the empirical function of the respondents. Empirical distribution function (sampling distribution function) is each x for the value X , $F^*(x) = \frac{n_x}{n}$ is said to be likely.

Here $n_x - x$ is smaller than, $x \leq x_1$ at $F^*(x) = 0$, x_n - even if it is the biggest option.

In short, the empirical function of the sample distribution serves to estimate the theoretical function of the population distribution. X_n we place the options in ascending order

Table 1.2 shows the responses of the sergeants to the survey questions
1.2 - table

options (consequence)	X_i	2	5	7	9	12	13	14	20
Frequency (repetition of an event)	n_i	6	7	10	4	4	4	8	7
...									

The size of the tests

$$n_i = n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + n_4 + n_5 + n_6 + n_7 + n_8 = 50$$

The smallest option is equal to 2, so

$$x < 2 \text{ at } F^*(x) = 0,$$

$x \leq 5$ value, $x_1 = 2$; 6 repeated times

$$2 < x \leq 5 \text{ da } F^*(x) = \frac{6}{50} = 0,12$$

$x \leq 7$ values, including $x_1 = 2$; $x_2 = 5$; qiymatlar $6+7=13$ times is observed, then

$$5 < x \leq 7 \text{ da } F^*(x) = \frac{13}{50} = 0,26$$

$x \leq 9$ values, including $x_1 = 2$; $x_2 = 5$; $x_3 = 7$; values, $6+7+10=23$ times is observed, then

$$7 < x \leq 9 \text{ da } F^*(x) = \frac{23}{50} = 0,46$$

$x \leq 12$ values, including $x_1 = 2$; $x_2 = 5$; $x_3 = 7$; $x_4 = 9$ values, $6+7+10+4=27$ times is observed, then

$$9 < x \leq 12 \text{ da } F^*(x) = \frac{27}{50} = 0,54$$

$x \leq 13$ values, including $x_1 = 2$; $x_2 = 5$; $x_3 = 7$; $x_4 = 9$; $x_5 = 12$; qiymatlar $6+7+10+4+4=31$ times is observed, then

$$12 < x \leq 13 \text{ da } F^*(x) = \frac{31}{50} = 0,62$$

$x \leq 14$ values, including $x_1 = 2$; $x_2 = 5$; $x_3 = 7$; $x_4 = 9$; $x_5 = 12$; $x_6 = 13$ values, $6+7+10+4+4+4=35$ times is observed, then

$$13 < x \leq 14 \text{ da } F^*(x) = \frac{35}{50} = 0,70$$

$x \leq 20$ values, including $x_1 = 2$; $x_2 = 5$; $x_3 = 7$; $x_4 = 9$; $x_5 = 12$; $x_6 = 13$; $x_7 = 14$ values, $6+7+10+4+4+4+8=43$ times is observed, then

$$14 < x \leq 20, F^*(x) = \frac{43}{50} = 0,86$$

$$x > 20 \text{ da } F^*(x) = 1$$

As a result of scientific research, the calculated theoretical empirical distribution function is expressed as follows:

$$F^*(x) = \begin{cases} x < 2 & \text{da } 0 \\ 2 < x \leq 5 & \text{da } 0,12 \\ 5 < x \leq 7 & \text{da } 0,26 \\ 7 < x \leq 9 & \text{da } 0,46 \\ 9 < x \leq 12 & \text{da } 0,54 \\ 12 < x \leq 13 & \text{da } 0,62 \\ 13 < x \leq 14 & \text{da } 0,70 \\ 14 < x \leq 20 & \text{da } 0,86 \\ x > 20 & \text{da } 1 \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

We construct the empirical function we are looking for:

Figure 1.1

Figure 1.1 depicts the graph of the empirical distribution function (theoretical analysis) of the scientific results of military sergeants based on questionnaires

As a result of scientific research - Sergeants - and cadets - received according to the results of the survey, both groups of respondents took part, and the correlation of the answers to 100 questions of eight types that are important for the military and the regression we construct equations (lines).

$$M(X) \approx \bar{x} = \sum_{i=1}^n / n ; M(Y) = \sum_{i=1}^y / n \approx \bar{y} ; \tag{1.2}$$

$$\sigma_x^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i^2}{n} - \bar{x}^2, \sigma_y^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i^2}{n} - \bar{y}^2; C_{xy} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i Y_i}{n} - \bar{x} \bar{y}$$

Here you can find the correlation coefficient using the following formula:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{C_{xy}}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}$$

We find the straight line of regression of Y on X from the data presented in Table 1.3

1.3.table

	X_i Serjan tlar	Y_i Kursa ntlar	X_i^2	Y_i^2	$x_i y_i$	zoh
	20	18	400	324	360	

	12	13	144	169	156	
	5	6	25	36	30	
	14	14	196	196	196	
	9	9	81	81	81	
	13	14	169	196	182	
	7	3	49	9	21	
	2	3	4	9	6	
$n=50$	$\sum_{x_i} = 82$	$\sum_{y_i} = 80$	$\sum_{x_i^2} = 1068$	$\sum_{y_i^2} = 1020$	$\sum_{x_i y_i} = 1032$	

From the table we get the following:

$$\sum_{i=1}^8 x_i = 82; \sum_{i=1}^8 y_i = 80; \sum_{i=1}^8 x_i^2 = 1068; \sum_{i=1}^8 y_i^2 = 1020; \sum_{i=1}^8 x_i y_i = 1032 \quad (1.3)$$

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^8 X_i}{n} = \frac{82}{50} = 1.64; \quad \bar{y} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^8 Y_i}{n} = \frac{80}{50} = 1.60;$$

$$\uparrow \sigma_x^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i^2}{n} - \bar{x}^2 = \frac{1068}{50} - 2.68 = 18.67; \sigma_x = 4.32;$$

$$\sigma_y^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i^2}{n} - \bar{y}^2 = \frac{1020}{50} - 2.56 = 17.84; \sigma_y = 4.22;$$

$$C_{xy} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i Y_i}{n} - \bar{x} \bar{y} = \frac{1032}{50} - 1.64 \cdot 1.60 = 20.64 - 2.62 = 18.02$$

If the multiplication $|r_{xy}| \cdot \sqrt{n-1} \geq 3$ if there is a correlation between the values of X and Y (X-officers and Y-cadets) taken at random, it will be sufficiently probable. That is, it shows that there is a possible linear relationship between them. If a linear approximation is established between X and Y, $\bar{y}_x$ from x to the linear regression formula is written as follows.

The linear regression equation is as follows

$$\bar{y}_x - \bar{y} = r_{xy} \cdot \frac{\sigma_y}{\sigma_x} (x - \bar{x}) \quad (1.4)$$

If we put the obtained results into the formula (1.4) and calculate,

$$\bar{y}_x - 1,60 = 0,99 \cdot \frac{4,22}{4,32} (x - 1,64); \quad \bar{y}_x - 1,60 = 0,96 \cdot (x - 1,64) = 0,96x - 1,57; \quad \bar{y}_x = 0,96x + 1,60 - 1,57 = 0,96x + 0,03$$

$$\bar{y}_x = 0,96x + 0,03$$

as well as

$$\bar{x}_y - \bar{x} = r_{xy} \cdot \frac{\sigma_x}{\sigma_y} (y - \bar{y}) \quad (1.5)$$

$$\bar{x}_y - 1,64 = 0,99 \cdot \frac{4,32}{4,22} (y - 1,60); \quad \bar{x}_y - 1,64 = 1,01(y - 1,60) = 1,01y - 1,62; \quad \bar{x}_y = 1,01y + 0,02$$

A correlation table representing the ratio of to and
Table 1.4

No	X_i Serge ants	Y_i Stude nts	$\bar{y}_x$	$\bar{x}_y$	$\bar{y}_x - \bar{x}_y$
1	20	18	19,32	18,20	1,11
2	12	13	11,60	13,15	-1,56
3	5	6	4,84	6,08	-1,24
4	14	14	13,53	14,16	-0,64
5	9	9	8,70	9,11	-0,41
6	13	14	12,56	14,16	-1,60
7	7	3	6,77	3,05	3,72
8	2	3	1,95	3,05	-1,11

Based on the data presented in the correlation table 1.4 below, we construct the equations of the regression straight lines of.

Figure 1.2

Figure 1.2 shows the regression equations representing the attitudes of sergeants and cadets to the process of radicalization

In order to evaluate the real value of the conducted scientific research, the real value is unknown, with equal (same) accuracy $n = 50$ let it be the results of the trial conducted once. The results of separate studies $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$ as a random variable. These quantities are arbitrary, have the same mathematical expectation (the true value of the sought (measured) quantity), the same $\sigma^2(x_1)$ and are normally distributed (experiments confirm this assumption). The actual value of the scientific research (quantity being measured) is equal to its mathematical expectation. Therefore, the problem is the mathematical expectation σ - mean square deviation, $\bar{x}$ - arithmetic mean value and mathematical expectation $\gamma = 0,95$ based on the double inequality with reliability values, it is given in intermediate evaluation. Thus, using the Student's distribution, it is unknown a parameter γ (0.95, 0.99, 0.999) which determines with reliability $\bar{x} - t_\gamma \cdot \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}} < a < \bar{x} + t_\gamma \cdot \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$ (1.6)

we find the confidence interval (interval). First of all, we will consider the mathematical statistical analysis of the reliability of the composition of the sergeants, the validity of the scientific research conducted on the basis of questionnaires, the accuracy of the assessment;

From table 1.3

$$\bar{x} = 82, \sigma_x = 4.32 \text{ va } [x] \text{ app } 3 t_\gamma = t(\gamma; n) \text{ } n = 50; t_\gamma(0,95; 50) = 2,009 [3]$$

(1.6) using the formula

$$82 - 2,009 \cdot \frac{4,32}{\sqrt{50}} < a_{as} < 82 + 2,009 \cdot \frac{4,32}{\sqrt{50}}$$

$$82 - 8,67 \cdot \frac{1}{7,07} < a_{as} < 82 + 8,67 \cdot \frac{1}{7,07}$$

$$82 - 1,23 < a_{as} < 82 + 1,23$$

$$80,77 < a_{as} < 83,23$$

The conclusions are that the processes of radicalism were mathematically analyzed in the section of military personnel (in today's era of globalization). On the eight most basic subjects, sergeants and cadets were rated with 0.95 (95%) accuracy and 0.05 (5%) deviation. Table 1.4 shows that the patriotism of sergeants and cadets- x_1 , trust- x_4 , the will - x_5 and pride- x_6 the answers to the relevant questions are almost the same, from which it can be concluded that

their outlook on such questions is the same. It is noteworthy that humanitarian pride and indomitable will had the same answer, so the regression line $M(13;14)$ at the point $\bar{y}_x$ and $\bar{x}_y$ ($\bar{y}_x$ -trust of sergeants to cadets, and the relationship of cadets to sergeants) shows that it is the closest (see Figure 1.2). It should be noted that the interim assessment obtained by sergeants and cadets based on the theoretical results of our scientific work on the processes of radicalism

$$80,77 < a_{as} < 83,23.$$

Today, it is considered a high result, the practical proof of this is that institutions belonging to the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan record record results in the world Olympiads, as a clear fact, professional training took place at the Chirchik Oliy Tank Command Engineering Educational Institution. the international science olympiad among the cadets can be cited as an example.

It is not without benefit to carry out such a questionnaire suddenly, during work processes or during military service recruitment. As a proposal, we believe that it is possible to eliminate or reduce the tendency of young people to this process, if questions adapted to the processes of radicalism are created in mathematics lessons in militarized lyceums and schools. For example, we can use it in classes of grouping, substitution, combinatorics elements.

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